

FIXED FUNDS EFFICIENCY UNDER DIFFERENT OWNERSHIP CONDITIONS

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Abstract: Property polyformism characteristic of the market economy is brought about by the transformation of private property. Community property is formed when private property is united by the will of its owners. When private property is nationalized, it becomes state property. The importance of state funds in the development of economic development and social spheres, their role in the budget, recommendations aimed at the effective use of financial resources of state funds were considered.

Key words: Private property, ownership system, macroeconomic, budget deficit, auction sale, market system

INTRODUCTION

Expropriation and privatization of property as one of the main conditions for the transition to market relations. With this, the state monopoly was abolished, the administrative order was broken, and the market economy was founded, a class of owners was formed, and production efficiency increased using foreign investment. Privatization of property and formation of multi-level economy was implemented in Uzbekistan in two stages. The first stage was implemented in 1992-1993. During this period, mainly household services, trade enterprises, small transport and construction enterprises, and processing enterprises changed their property form, and lease, collective, and shareholding forms of property appeared. Houses were privatized.

The second stage was carried out on the basis of the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 21, 1994 "On further

deepening of economic reforms, protection of private property interests and measures to develop entrepreneurship". During this period, open joint-stock companies were externalized, companies issued their shares, it was planned to sell state property to individuals through auction, and complete privatization.

Private property - property owned by certain people or households; the leading form of property among various types of property in a market economy. The object of private property is material and financial assets, labor, intellectual labor products, land, water, underground resources, enterprises, farms, stocks and bonds, money, vehicles, housing, consumer goods. , work ability, business skills, scientific discoveries, technical inventions, works of art and literature, etc. can be. The subject of private property is considered to be the people who own it, certain individuals and households.

Private property is the oldest form of ownership, the collective property that grew out of the collective property of tribes and clans a few thousand years ago passed into the hands of some people and turned into private property. Private property was considered the main property in the traditional and market system. The planned economic system eliminated private property and established state property, declaring consumer property, including household goods and real estate, as private property. After the return from the planned system to the market economy, Private property will be restored anew. This is achieved by:

- 1) state property is converted into private property;
- 2) it is allowed to create private property at the expense of private funds;
- 3) private property is separated from community (collective farm) property;
- 4) estates and household property, which are considered personal property, are given the status of Private property;
- 5) Private property comes from abroad and is added to the existing ownership system.

Private property is characterized by a number of signs as the basis of the market economy: Private property ensures the appropriation of economic resources,

created products and services, and wealth in general by individual individuals or families. Private property owners can be different types of people, such as entrepreneurs, workers, servants, farmers, landowners and rentiers. Private property gives its owner economic power, that is, it provides him with the function of management. The property is managed by the owner himself or by managers on his behalf. Private property must benefit its owner. Private property gives its owner economic independence, that is, the property owner uses it as he sees fit. The owner of the property decides what to do according to the rule of alternative economic choice, whether he puts the property into business, sells it, mortgages it, or bequeaths it.

Methods and recommendations

Private property should be economically realized - it should bring property income to its owner or satisfy his consumption needs. Laws adopted by the state and unwritten rules, that is, established traditions and property rights, ensure ownership of private property, property rights. In Uzbekistan, the inviolability of private property is recognized in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and laws on property.

Private property in Uzbekistan was created as a result of the privatization of state property, permission to create it, and private enterprises, farms and peasant farms, private banks, estates, household property and money savings, securities were transferred to the object of private property. turned.

Private property is divided into 2 types according to the method of its economic realization;

1) private individual private property belonging to some people. The ownership of this property occurs through the owner's own activity, it is managed by the owner individually, the income he brings goes directly to the owner without being divided into shares;

2) corporate, group Private property. Its owners are shareholders, whose ownership is measured by the value of the shares in their hands. In this type of private

property, the economic realization of the property occurs not individually, but within the group of owners. This property is managed not by the shareholders themselves, but by hired managers, and the income from it is distributed among the shareholders according to the rule of ownership and is in the form of dividends. While Small Private Property is individual, Large Private Property has the characteristics of corporate Private Property.

It is known that the state budget, which is the centralized monetary fund of the state, collects funds from various sources and through various means (taxes, fees, duties, mandatory payments), and in turn, these funds are used for various purposes. and spent in directions (for example, education, healthcare, culture, economy, public administration, etc.). In this case, a specific type of income is not attached to cover a specific type of expense. In this respect, the state budget is a universal monetary fund. However, the current budget legislation requires funds to be spent on specific directions, cost groups and items. In such conditions, there is a need to provide stable funding for certain socio-economic needs from specific sources, because there is a risk of reducing the expenditures intended for these purposes in the period of economic tension, instability and, as a result, budget deficits. . Therefore, it is important to determine the most important directions of socio-economic development in the society and to ensure the targeted use of funds.

These circumstances served as a serious basis for the establishment of appropriate extra-budgetary special funds for the financing of a number of public tasks.

State trust funds included in the consolidated budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan, such as the state budget, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Budget Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the "State budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan" adopted by the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan for each financial year "On" and other legal documents are established and valid.

Conclusions

In short, at the current stage of economic and social development, budget revenues are increasing with the development of production, the growth of incomes of economic entities and the population, the expansion of tax bases, and the increase of property forms. However, in this period, the multi-disciplinary needs of the society did not decrease, on the contrary, new activities, projects, directions appeared, which were objectively necessary to be financed from the state budget. Funding them in full will require raising more funds. But the ability to continuously increase revenues (in particular, by increasing taxes) is limited by the current tax legislation and the economic capabilities of taxpayers. At the same time, an unjustified increase in taxes seriously harms the economic activities of economic entities, extinguishes their interest in the development of production and increasing its efficiency. In such conditions, it is not always possible to achieve a balance of budget expenditures with budget revenues. As a result, the state faces another important macroeconomic issue - the issue of maintaining the budget deficit at an economically safe level.

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